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Task Name: Crown Challenge/TASK1

Method Description

The proposed CNN model comprises a feature extraction module and a classification module. The feature extraction module consists of two parallel networks, namely 3D Residual Network and 2D Residual Network. The 3D Residual Network captures the relevant features from the 3D MRA volume, and the 2D Residual Network extracts the spatial information from the 2D Maximum Intensity Projection (MIP) image of the input MRA volume. The feature extraction block uses the residual skip connection in the 3D and 2D Residual Networks. Then the combined features from the parallel modules are fed into the Anterior and Posterior classification heads. The classification module uses a fully connected layer for the stratification task.